

Interactive Visualization of Linked Open Data Networks Representing Historical Writings

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Alassi Sepideh. 2024. "Interactive Visualization of Linked Open Data Networks Representing Historical Writings", *Historical Network Research 2024*, Lausanne, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12598807

Recent projects leverage linked open data (LOD) principles to create digital editions of historical writings, focusing on correspondence and diaries. While RDF technologies enhance machine-readable editions, the resulting graph remains hidden from web application users, limiting their comprehension of data connectivity. Visualizing RDF data empowers scholars to analyze distributions, detect irregularities, and formulate new research questions. This paper introduces three generic interactive web-based tools for visualizing RDF graphs, specifically those of historical correspondence networks and travel diaries. The tools offer 3D force-directed graphs for correspondence networks, 3D DAG-force trees to track correspondence topic changes over time, and maps for displaying journey routes in travel diaries.

To prevent node and edge overlap, the first two visualizations are in three dimensions and are force-directed. For the readability of a visualized network, since the 1990s it has been advocated that the number of edge crossings must be minimized (Grandjean, 2019). To generate graphs free of edge-crossing without reducing graph size, force-directed layout algorithms are developed (see Hu 2005, Nooy 2003, and Kobourov, 2012), which can be implemented in web applications using ThreeJS/WebGL;⁸ the resulting 3D graphs can then be rendered on the web. The visualization tools offer interactive features such as moving graph components, zooming, and changing camera views. Configuration parameters (e.g., node and line colors) and RDF data in JSON/JSON-LD format are input for visualization. Nodes in the graphs are linked to underlying RDF resources, enabling users to navigate from visualizations to the textual source with a click. These visualization tools support an exploratory and methodological approach to studying graphs, empowering researchers to delve into the data accompanied by explanations of sources and relations.

3D Force-Directed Correspondence Graph Visualization

The visualization tool can render any RDF graph as a 3D force-directed graph on the web, allowing interaction with the simulation (Alassi et al. 2020). This simulation tightens connections between connected vertices and pushes unconnected ones apart, achieving a symmetric and aesthetically pleasing layout. The iterative engine seeks a mechanical equilibrium for the system of springs, resulting in well-recognizable clusters without overlapping edges. In the initial stage, the graph appears tangled but evolves into a stable layout. In correspondence network visualization, to avoid overcrowding, nodes representing RDF resources of correspondents and letters, along with edges for three main RDF predicates (`hasAuthor`, `hasRecipient`, `isReplyTo`), are included in the graph (Figure 1).

⁸ <https://threejs.org/>

Figure 1. An example of the 3D visualization of RDF triples.

Figure 2. Visualization of the correspondence of mathematicians of the Bernoulli dynasty.

Figure 2 depicts the correspondence network of the Bernoulli dynasty members⁹ that are available online as RDF-based digital editions with full transcriptions and facsimiles (Alassi, Rosenthaler 2024).¹⁰ Among Bernoulli mathematicians, Johann Bernoulli was the one who corresponded intensively with prominent persons of his time; he not only kept the letters he received, but he also kept a draft of the letters he authored. Thus, our database contains an extensive number of letters sent or received by Johann Bernoulli, and the node representing him in the graph has a higher degree which puts him in the center point of the force-directed graph. The visualizations reveal significant correspondence by Johann I Bernoulli with renowned mathematicians, especially with Swiss mathematicians Johann Jakob Scheuchzer¹¹ and Johannes Scheuchzer,¹² forming noticeable clusters. The visualization also shows Jacob Hermann's correspondence

⁹ https://vis.beol.dasch.swiss/myLetterNetwork_3D/graphs/bebbCorrespondence/

¹⁰ <https://dhlab-journey-star.dhlab.unibas.ch/>

¹¹ <http://ark.dasch.swiss/ark:/72163/1/0801/rE1GJDa6SQicRl11FhwNgAo>

¹² <http://ark.dasch.swiss/ark:/72163/1/0801/4o5cyqGYS1qHTfFCTMDDzwM>

with Johann I Bernoulli, which began in 1702, three years before the death of Jacob Bernoulli,¹³ Hermann's master. Considering the conflict between the Bernoulli brothers, one wonders about the nature of the correspondence between Jacob's disciple and his rival. This question can be answered by studying the underlying resources connected to the graph nodes.

The correspondence networks are also visualized in Web-VR format to enable direct interaction with the network components as if they were real objects in the same 3D spatial dimensions as the viewer, increasing the tangibility of the visualized network.¹⁴ The VR version of the visualization tool uses A-Frame¹⁵ for rendering the 3D force-directed graphs. Therefore, it can only be used by the full-fledged VR devices that support A-Frame.

3D DAG-Force Tree Visualization of Hierarchical Information

Hierarchical tree structures can be visualized as a 3D DAG (Directed Acyclic Graph) Force Tree, which prevents the overlap of nodes and edges based on the repulsive and attractive forces assigned to the nodes. Since this kind of visualization is directed and does not contain loops, it is best suited for visualizing hierarchical tree structures such as RDF lists (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. A hierarchical RDF list representing the correspondence topics.

Having modeled the correspondence topics as such a list, we could then visualize the correspondence network categorized by the topics of the letters. Moreover, a slider widget in the tool, representing the date of the letter with year precision, allows users to study the change in the topic of correspondence over time. This slider triggers the highlighting of the nodes representing the letters authored at the chosen year by changing the node colors to red. The graph nodes are connected to the underlying RDF resource representing the letter transcription; thus, users are directed to the source document from the visualization through a simple right-click on a node.

The visualization of the Euler-Goldbach correspondence in this way, for example, shows that at the beginning of their correspondence, Leonhard Euler¹⁶ and Christian Goldbach¹⁷ mostly discussed mathematical topics, starting with number theory and continuing with analysis and geometry (Figure 4a, b).¹⁸ Their correspondence had years of pause between 1732 and 1735 and later again between 1754 and 1755; a close study of the letter contents can reveal the reasons for these periods of pause in correspondence.¹⁹ Moreover, between 1746 and 1750, they mostly corresponded about astronomy and technology. This change in the topic of correspondence might be related to Euler's breakthrough in these subjects in this period, especially astronomy. The visualization also exhibits that the topic of their

¹³ <https://ark.dasch.swiss/ark:/72163/1/0801/6E07Zq0RRTeRnBreFKB=TQF.20211025T081140028236Z>

¹⁴ Other correspondence visualizations and Web-VR visualizations can be found here: <https://vis.beol.dasch.swiss/>

¹⁵ <https://aframe.io/>

¹⁶ https://ark.dasch.swiss/ark:/72163/1/0801/NbmhfOBIQoGbX3HwXuC3Tg_.20191028T092209709Z

¹⁷ https://ark.dasch.swiss/ark:/72163/1/0801/EVAEahjpR_e6IXOWX=RVzQS.20191028T092209716Z

¹⁸ https://vis.beol.dasch.swiss/myLetterNetwork_3D/graphs/subjectVisualization/

¹⁹ Digital Edition of some of Leonhard Euler's correspondence, including his entire correspondence series with Christian Goldbach with English translations, can be found at <https://bernoulli-euler.dhlab.unibas.ch/biography/Leonhard%20Euler>

correspondence, over time, shifted toward personal matters. Towards the end, between 1763 and 1764, the number of letters exchanged decreased. Studying the highlighted letters written in this period shows that Goldbach's health was declining; thus, he reduced his communication, stating that “with every year that goes by, I am reading and writing less.”²⁰

Figure 4a. The topic of the Euler-Goldbach correspondence in 1730 was mainly mathematics.

Figure 4b. The topic of the Euler-Goldbach correspondence in 1763 was mainly personal life.

Visualization of Journey Routes on Maps

Travel diaries, both modern and historical, detail routes, transportation, accommodation, activities, and individuals, each accompanied by metadata like dates and information sources. RDF-star²¹ technology facilitates the efficient representation of travel records as linked open data, with metadata attached to graph edges (Alassi 2022, Amman et al. 2023). The journey information, such as routes and stages, can then be retrieved from the graph database using SPARQL-star. In 2023, an interactive RDF-star-based digital edition of Jacob Bernoulli's travel diary, Reisbüchlein, was created as part of a project funded by the

²⁰ <http://ark.dasch.swiss/ark:/72163/1/0801/v5mma7PzTcOD8ZndsBBDVAq>

²¹ https://w3c.github.io/rdf-star/cg-spec/editors_draft.html

University of Basel.²² To aid scholars in visualizing journeys without constant map references, a dynamic web-based visualization tool was developed that retrieves data about the stages of the journey from the triplestore and displays it on an interactive map. To prevent creating yet another silo containing location information, coordinates, and GeoName-IDs of locations, they are obtained dynamically from LOD-based repositories like Wikidata through federated searches and used for map visualizations. Having the coordinates of the locations, the journeys are visualized on interactive web components based on Angular 16 and the Leaflet plug-in²³ of the OpenStreetMap. Figure 5 illustrates Jacob Bernoulli's journey from Basel to Geneva in 1676, given as the first entry in his travel diary *Reisbüchlein* and all stages of this journey.²⁴ Figure 6 illustrates his journey mostly on foot from Paris to Basel in 17 stages in 1680.²⁵

Figure 5. Jacob Bernoulli's journey from Basel to Geneva in 1676.

Figure 6. Jacob Bernoulli's journey from Paris to Basel in 1680.

²² The RDF-star-based digital edition of Jacob Bernoulli's *Reisbüchlein* with map visualizations is available at <https://bernoulli-euler.dhlab.unibas.ch/biography/Jacob%20I%20Bernoulli>

²³ <https://www.npmjs.com/package/leaflet>

²⁴ The digital edition of Jacob Bernoulli's entry in his travel diary *Reisbüchlein* about his journey from Basel to Geneva with transcriptions, journey information, and dynamic visualization can be found at <https://bernoulli-euler.dhlab.unibas.ch/manuscriptEntry/http:%2F%2Frdfh.ch%2F0801%2FGcXDoaZgRu6E2scC77h6gw>

²⁵ The digital edition of Jacob Bernoulli's entry in his travel diary *Reisbüchlein* about his journey from Paris to Basel with transcriptions, journey information, and dynamic visualization can be found at https://bernoulli-euler.dhlab.unibas.ch/manuscriptEntry/http:%2F%2Frdfh.ch%2F0801%2F_KaGmqZLTyW9U9__vCUzLA

Conclusion

This paper describes tools to create three types of visualization for RDF-based networks, facilitating the study of the relations between network components and connectedness of atoms of knowledge present in LOD-based scholarly editions. The first described visualization enables the representation of data networks, such as correspondence, as interactive web-based 3D-force-directed graphs that help with the observation of the data distribution and connectivity, preventing data loss due to overlaps of graph components. The second visualization type enables visualizing hierarchical and categorical data structures, for example, correspondence clustered by topics as interactive web-based 3D DAG force trees, which preserve the hierarchical structure of data clusters by preventing loops and overlap of nodes and edges. With an example, I have shown how this visualization can be enhanced to represent more data by adding widgets, for example, to allow the study of the change in the topic of correspondence over time. Through interaction with this kind of visualization, scholars gain knowledge about the data that would not be so readily accessible and would require a comprehensive close study of texts. With multiple examples, this paper has established the benefits of these two graph visualization tools, illustrating that through studying and interacting with the graph, scholars can obtain a picture of the data connections and formulate questions that can then be answered through the close study of the underlying sources. Thus, conjoining the visualizations with the text sources as implemented for the graphs presented in this paper is important to facilitate scholarly research on the data.

The paper also suggests a third visualization tool for representing map data in interactive form on web applications. This paper presents a use case for this tool for an interactive web-based representation of Jacob Bernoulli's travel routes retrieved from the RDF-star-based digital edition of his travel diary. The map visualization tool benefits from the possibility of retrieving coordinate data for locations from the external linked open data repositories through federated searches and dynamically generating the visualizations upon access. The three visualization tools will be extended, and a generic Angular-based tool will be developed to be easily integrated into the web applications so that other projects can produce similar visualizations for their RDF graphs. This tool will also be able to generate visualizations based on the results of customized CONSTRUCT queries submitted to the SPARQL endpoint of the target triplestore.

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